

D7.6 Webinars report

Task 7.4.2 European (International) level webinars

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1. Document History

1.1 Location

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2. Executive summary

The PilotSTRATEGY project is investigating geological CO₂ storage sites in industrial regions of Southern and Eastern Europe to support development of large-scale carbon capture and storage (CCS). Research is focused on deep saline aquifers (DSA) – porous rock formations filled with brine several kilometres below ground – which promise a large capacity for storing CO₂ captured from clusters of industry. Detailed studies are being carried out on DSAs in the Paris Basin in France, the Lusitanian Basin in Portugal and the Ebro Basin in Spain. The project is also enhancing knowledge and understanding of CO₂ storage options in West Macedonia in Greece and Upper Silesia in Poland. PilotSTRATEGY also engages with citizens and stakeholders to ensure that community perspectives are fully represented in the project. This report fulfils the requirements of Task 7.4.2 European (International) level webinars, as part of WP7 Communications & Impact.

Webinars (online seminars) are online videoconferences that can be held exclusively for a selected audience of targeted stakeholders, so are suitable for communication between project partners and specific audiences such as researchers, industry, policy makers, general public and other stakeholders. As part of the objectives outlined in D7.2 “Communication and Dissemination plan”, the PilotSTRATEGY project organised set of eight webinars — seven project webinars and one joint webinar — with the purpose of disseminating key project outcomes to a wide European and International public audience.

The first project webinar (Webinar 1) took place in 2023. The following year, Webinars 2-6 were organised as part of an Autumn Webinar Series that took place over October-November 2024, covering each of the five project regions. The seventh webinar was a joint webinar in 2025, organised together with the COREu project (Horizon Europe). The final project webinar (Webinar 7) took place in March 2026.

These webinars were used to share methodologies, case studies, results, best practices and other information between regions and to stakeholders at a global level. All webinars were run using accessible platforms, where participants could listen and interact during question/answer sessions in real time. All webinars were recorded and made available on the project’s [YouTube channel](#) and website. Having an archive of webinars available to watch after project ends will support the long-term exploitation of the project’s results.

This report provides a summary of each webinar, including dates, presenters, overview of the content covered, attendance analytics, and links to recordings.

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3. Webinar 1 - Community Acceptance: First explorations of regions

Date: 17 May 2023

Description

This webinar focused on the results of the deliverable on Social Acceptance and Community Engagement. The findings of regional community profiles developed through interviews, media analyses and other approaches, as well as results of a first wave of surveys on community acceptance were presented. These were shown in an overview for the five regions of the PilotSTRATEGY countries (Spain, Portugal, France, Greece, Poland) and as a case study for Portugal. Furthermore, this webinar presented the engagement of key stakeholders during the first regional stakeholder committees. The webinar featured a Q&A session with presenters and additional panellists from CIEMAT, SYMLOG, Fraunhofer ISE, and University of Lisbon.

Speakers: Romain Viguier (SCCS), Elisabeth Dütschke (Fraunhofer ISI), Ana Delicado (University of Lisbon), Sabine Preuß (Fraunhofer ISI)

Link to event on website: <https://pilotstrategy.eu/events/webinar-1-community-acceptance-first-explorations-regions>

Link to recording: https://youtu.be/1xpEIGp5GNE?si=g9sOyUbwmyF_5aof

Registrants	Attendees	Attendance rate ¹
108	59	55%

¹ Average attendee engagement rate

4. Webinar 2 - Advancing offshore CO₂ storage in Portugal

Date: 17 October 2024

Description

This webinar presented the current status of research for the implementation of a CO₂ injection site in the offshore Lusitanian basin, Portugal. Speakers introduced the project within the framework of CCUS scenarios for Portugal and its relevance for hard-to-abate sectors, and described the work conducted towards the characterisation and design of the injection site. Furthermore, the webinar addressed the stakeholder engagement approaches and interaction with the general public. The webinar featured a Q&A session with presenters from University of Évora, GALP, and University of Lisbon.

Speakers: Júlio Carneiro, (University of Évora), João Casação (GALP), Ana Delicado (University of Lisbon)

Link to event on website: <https://pilotstrategy.eu/events/webinar-2-advancing-offshore-co2-storage-portugal>

Link to recording: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=KXf8x91A6yY>

Registrants	Attendees	Attendance rate
85	60	71%

5. Webinar 3 - Upper Silesia, Poland: Activities, results, challenges

Date: 24 October 2024

Description

This webinar presented and discussed with participants the activities carried out for selected regions in Poland where CO₂ storage could potentially be possible. During the meeting, the scope and results of the work were discussed, with particular emphasis on the results of the geological conditions of selected locations, storage potential, related challenges and actions necessary to be taken. Legal conditions for the use of technology in Poland and social acceptance and community engagement in CCS technology development were also discussed.

Speakers: Krzysztof Stańczyk, Tomasz Urych and Aleksandra Koteras - Central Mining Institute (GIG)

Link to event on website: <https://pilotstrategy.eu/events/webinar-3-upper-silesia-poland-activities-results-challenges>

Link to recording: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=XlqHlu_tNOY

Registrants	Attendees	Attendance rate
57	53	93%

6. Webinar 4 - Investigation & prospects of CCS technology for climate change mitigation in Greece, West Macedonia

Date: 31 October 2024

Description

Over the past five years, West Macedonia has served as a pilot for implementing CCS technology, with the Mesohellenic trough identified as a promising candidate. The insights gained from this initiative will serve as a knowledge base for deploying similar solutions in other suitable locations across Greece. This webinar aimed to delve into CCS technology, its economic feasibility, and its implications for addressing climate change.

Speakers: Dr. Nikolaos Koukouzas (CERTH), Dr. Dimitrios Ktena (HEREMA)

Link to event on website: <https://pilotstrategy.eu/events/webinar-4-investigation-and-prospects-ccs-technology-climate-change-mitigation-greece-west>

Link to recording: <https://youtu.be/UbWAnGdWZwA?si=fxXLFCfrIEJwem-O>

Registrants	Attendees	Attendance rate
60	49	82%

7. Webinar 5 - Onshore CO₂ Storage in the Paris Basin: An Overview of Geological, Technical, and Social Studies

Date: 07 November 2024

Description

Since 2021, the French partners BRGM, IFPEN, SYMLOG, GEOSTOCK, and Pôle Avenia have been conducting an in-depth assessment of the potential for geological CO₂ storage in the Paris Basin. The study explores the feasibility of using deep saline aquifers (DSAs) for CO₂ storage to advance carbon capture and storage (CCS) technology, a key driver in the transition to net-zero emissions. In this webinar, the speakers shared mid-project results and discussed future perspectives through 2026. A Q&A session followed, offering participants the chance to engage with the scientists involved.

Speakers: Aurélien Bordenave (BRGM)

Panelists: Isaline Gravaud (BRGM), Thomas Le Guenan (BRGM), Aurélien Bordenave (BRGM), Claire Mays (Symlog), Sarah Bouquet (IFPEN), Audrey Estublier (IFPEN).

Link to event on website: <https://pilotstrategy.eu/events/webinar-5-onshore-co2-storage-paris-basin-overview-geological-technical-and-social-studies>

Link to recording: <https://youtu.be/KadLSrdW1AU?si=ZQK5ryd7obqksnFn>

Registrants	Attendees	Attendance rate
121	77	64%

8. Webinar 6 - Onshore CO₂ storage in Spain: An overview of geological, technical, economic and social assessments

Date: 14 November 2024

Description

From 2021, the Spanish partners IGME, CIEMAT and REPSOL have been studying in detail the potential for CO₂ geological storage at a site in the Lopin structure, located in NE Spain (Zaragoza, Ebro Basin). The objective is to pave the way for future CO₂ geological storage developments based on geological, technical, economic, legal (including permitting) and social results and recommendations. In this webinar, an overview of the current state of the studies was presented, as well as planned activities until the end of the project in 2026.

Speakers: Paula Canteli (IGME), Francisco Pángaro (Repsol), Jesús García Crespo (IGME), Manuel Ron (Repsol), Christian Oltra (CIEMAT)

Link to event on website: <https://pilotstrategy.eu/events/webinar-6-onshore-co2-storage-spain-overview-geological-technical-economic-and-social>

Link to recording: <https://youtu.be/hCT6q6xbHsM>

Registrants	Attendees	Attendance rate
154	109	71%

9. Joint Webinar PilotSTRATEGY + COREu - Geological Perspectives on CO₂ Storage in Central Europe: Czech Republic and Poland

Date: 24 November 2025

Description

As Europe moves toward climate neutrality, geological CO₂ storage plays a vital role in enabling large-scale Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS) deployment. This joint Lunch & Learn session brought together experts from COREu (Horizon Europe) and PilotSTRATEGY (Horizon 2020) - two European projects addressing CO₂ storage from complementary perspectives. The event explored geological case studies from the Czech Republic and Poland, covering the journey from site exploration and characterisation to reservoir simulation and storage potential assessment. Participants gained insights into regional opportunities, challenges, and research outcomes that support the development of future CO₂ storage hubs in Central Europe.

Speakers: Thiago Lima Silva (SINTEF ER), Isaline Gravaud (BRGM), Karel Bříza (MND a.s.), Tomasz Urych (Central Mining Institute Poland)

Link to event on website: <https://pilotstrategy.eu/events/geological-perspectives-co2-storage-central-europe-czech-republic-and-poland>

Link to recording: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=enkEdP-8Ms0>

Registrants	Attendees	Attendance rate
109	78	72%

10. Webinar 7 - Citizen Engagement in PilotSTRATEGY: What Communities Are Telling Us

Date: 26 March 2026

Description

What do citizens really think about CO₂ storage? This webinar shared key findings from PilotSTRATEGY citizen engagement activities across three European regions. Speakers shared what citizens highlighted as priorities, concerns, and expectations, and how these inputs can inform project communication and community engagement practices. The session started with an overview of the social science research conducted by the project and closed with a moderated Q&A.

Speakers: Sabine Preuß (Fraunhofer ISI), Ana Delicado (University of Lisbon), Christian Oltra (Ciemat), Claire Mays (Symlog)

Link to event on website: <https://pilotstrategy.eu/events/webinar-7-citizen-engagement-pilotstrategy-what-communities-are-telling-us>

Link to recording: <https://youtu.be/2hpeongdTic?si=xC-nuWhl2Mwaj1i4>

Registrants	Attendees	Attendance rate
74	50	68%

11. Conclusion

The PilotSTRATEGY webinars fulfilled the objectives outlined in D7.2 “Communication and Dissemination plan”. Eight webinars were carried out in total — seven project webinars and one joint webinar — with the purpose of disseminating key project outcomes to a wide European and International public audience.

The first project webinar, Webinar 1 – Community Acceptance: First Explorations of Regions, focused on the work carried out under Work Package 6 (WP6) – Social Acceptance, and presented findings from the first wave of surveys on community acceptance. Webinars 2–6 then showcased results from each of the project’s focus regions — Portugal, Poland, Greece, France and Spain, respectively. An additional webinar was co-organised with the COREu project, demonstrating the value of collaboration across Horizon projects.

The final project webinar, Webinar 7 – *Citizen Engagement in PilotSTRATEGY: What Communities Are Telling Us*, also centred on WP6 – Social Acceptance, bringing the series full circle by returning to the social dimension that opened it. It presented insights from five years of social science research conducted throughout the project.

In total, the webinars attracted over 530 live attendees, with the recordings receiving more than 340 additional views. All project webinars are available on the project’s [YouTube channel](#), and added to the project website.